

Integrating Sensing and Communications for Future Interactive, Immersive, and Intelligent Connectivity

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Abstract—Future wireless connectivity is envisioned to accommodate functionalities far beyond broadband data transmission, taking into account environmental parameters and usage scenario characteristics. In this landscape, the concept of integrated sensing and communication (ISAC) introduces a new *beyond communications* paradigm shift, where communication nodes can be employed to sense the shape of surrounding obstacles, map the environment, detect the presence of objects, focus power, localize users and track mobility. In this article, the roadmap for interactive, immersive and intelligent connectivity is presented with respect to different usage scenarios, involving mobility and environmental awareness. It is analyzed how the ISAC opportunity can be transformed into a powerful 6G enabler for an intelligent beyond-communications network capable of sensing the world. In this context, ISAC is envisioned to emerge from the synthesis of three visionary pillars: sense-to-communicate, communicate-to-sense, and multifunctional ISAC connectivity.

Index Terms—integrated sensing and communication, 6G, localization, sensing.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE evolution beyond 5G is gradually shifting from the necessity to *just transmit bits* into *connectivity beyond just communications*. For the first time, networks are not considered as communication-centric anymore; they provide multi-functional connectivity, including sensing, monitoring, and imaging. This transition involves major challenges in broadband and efficient communication for everyone and everywhere, immersive connectivity for complicated or even abstracted environments (e.g. augmented reality), and network intelligitization. A common characteristic among these trends is that they go beyond the conventional connectivity approach in 5G; they target efficient transmission and reception of information, to enable a wide range of applications, from concepts that relate to the semantics of the information, to understanding, mapping and re-programming the wireless environment. In recent years, research in industry and academia has revolved around identifying critical scenarios for 6G connectivity and inventing powerful and cost/power efficient enablers to address the corresponding challenges. There seems to be an agreement among the various stakeholders that critical usage scenarios will include a group of extreme evolution of the well-known 5G usage scenarios and a group of revolutionary usage scenarios with a clear emphasis on *beyond communications* objectives [1].

Radio frequency (RF) sensing and wireless communications are usually performed in separate systems, in distinct platforms and in non-cooperative or even competitive settings. They have different objectives and performance criteria; for example, data rate or quality of service in communications and detection probability or statistical performance in terms of Cramér-Rao Bound (CRB) in target parameter estimation. They can coexist within the same spectrum, yet, there is no information exchange between them to mitigate interference, optimize performance, or adjust operational parameters. Therefore, there is a compelling need for performing communications and sensing jointly, so that signals considered to be interferences in non-cooperative settings can be exploited for sensing or communications purposes, with efficient spectrum usage and hardware/circuit cost reduction.

In view of the ongoing effort for convergence among radar and communications multiantenna technologies, multifunction hardware designs, and waveform adaptivity, there is an excellent opportunity to bring together advanced radar and sensing technologies, breakthrough material science and cyber-physical intelligence into a unified framework and a coherent multifunction system concept. To this end, Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) technologies are envisioned to provide unprecedented quality of experience towards reliable, resilient, and ubiquitous connectivity, beyond the transmission of bits [2]. By means of a novel notion of co-designing communications and sensing intelligence and leveraging breakthrough radar, intelligent surfaces and Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning (AI/ML) technologies for environment mapping and wavefront engineering, sensing becomes an integral functionality of network nodes, and the network becomes capable of sensing the world. In this landscape, the protection of Personally Identifiable Information (PII) of human users and sensitive components becomes more timely than ever, calling for a privacy preserving architecture, which could be achieved directly in the digital physical layer with secure signal processing features or even by using the reconfigurability embedded in the RF ISAC hardware to employ sensing KPI control [3]; both features could be combined to ensure a trustworthy-by-design ISAC system.

In this article, the concept of connectivity beyond communications is presented, where users, devices and systems *communicate to sense, sense to communicate* and are *hyperconnected in a multi-functional integrated and interactive fashion*, as visualized in Fig. 1. The transition to such a new wireless

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Fig. 1. System concept (left) and layered architecture (right), also showing the novel functionalities and performance metrics.

era is characterized by a multi-functional 6G system concept, in which spectrally and energy-efficient, immersive, interactive, reliable, and resilient connectivity in the bandwidth-rich mmWave and sub-THz regimes can be dynamically established and seamlessly reconfigured.

II. CONNECTIVITY BEYOND COMMUNICATIONS

Bringing to fruition the novel notion of co-designed and jointly optimized communications and sensing in 6G networks entails several challenges, including (a) introducing novel propagation and channel modeling principles and a novel communication theory approach, equipped with the appropriate waveforms, signaling, protocols and algorithms for ISAC; (b) devising a revolutionary approach to sensing -beyond the conventional sensor/actuator and radar concepts- where multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) systems, holographic radios, intelligent surfaces and so far unexplored capabilities for wavefront tunability are used to materialize beyond communications functionalities; and (c) delivering a flexible and powerful synthesis of sensing technologies, ISAC and AI/ML capabilities into a wireless network optimization framework.

In view of the above challenges, the roadmap to ISAC is envisioned to emerge from the synthesis of the following three visionary pillars.

A. Communicate-to-sense

The objective of the *communicate-to-sense* pillar is to take advantage of the communication aspect, to transform the wireless network into a smart *sense-the-world* platform, providing a wireless radio capable of sensing, detecting, mapping, and understanding semantics. Co-design of sensing and communications, and cooperation among wirelessly connected users is vital for supporting ISAC functionalities, both at the physical layer and at the network level, guaranteeing connectivity reliability, agility and reconfigurability.

To design *communications-aided sensing*, it is necessary to expand the conventional communications system paradigm, and introduce new performance targets, such as increasing the sensing, localization and mapping accuracy. This task requires using the network as a sensor, to provide different sensing services: positioning of the active users, localization of passive

objects that are not connected to the network, and learning the static environment at times when the network data traffic load is low or moderate. To this end, realistic channel and blockage models need to be incorporated to the design and optimisation, as well as realistic models for cell-free network architectures complemented with intelligent surfaces to support enhanced network operation, performance, and efficiency.

B. Sense-to-communicate

The objective of the *sense-to-communicate* pillar is to take advantage of sensing information, to substantially improve radio spectrum usage and support novel beyond-communications use cases. The integration of the sensing aspect in communications opens a new dimension and numerous degrees of freedom in modeling and virtually mapping the wireless environment, assisting wireless access technologies with contextual information, optimizing, adapting and learning transceiver operational parameters, and transforming the wireless systems towards deterministic networking principles materialization.

A key component for designing *sensing-aided communications* is to build and maintain awareness on the dynamic radio environment. Knowledge of the locations of mobile users can simplify beam alignment complexity and allow managing interferences and separating users in the spatial domain. To this end, sensing is necessary for building and learning situational awareness to enhance and optimize communications performance. This task requires the development of joint objective functions, rewards and regret models for optimization and learning, as well as the design of waveforms suitable for cooperative sensing and communications systems, along with information exchange with communications users to create and share awareness about radio environments and interferences.

C. Multi-functional ISAC network intelligence

The objective of *multi-functional ISAC network intelligence* is to leverage AI-based optimization for wireless ISAC systems and algorithm design, together with data-driven ML approaches, to optimise the architecture, resources allocation, propagation modeling and waveform design. Intelligence,

beam steering. With judicious design, the intelligent surface can generate nontrivial beams that are able to address the challenges of high frequencies (e.g. FR2, mmWave) more efficiently than conventional beam-forming [5]. For example, non-diffracting beams can mitigate the increased propagation attenuation, and bending beams, that is, beams that are able to propagate along a curved trajectory, can efficiently counteract blockage. Beams with self-healing properties, that is, beams that are able to reconstruct after being interrupted by a small blocker, open up new possibilities for resilient connectivity. Focused beams are ideal for concentrating the transmitted power in small areas, a key element for energy efficient communications and localization applications.

IV. INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES FOR ISAC

A. Communicate-to-sense

1) *RIS-as-a-sensor*: The ability of the RIS to focus the power of the reflected beam in a small area is ideal for localization applications. By leveraging the communication between the RIS and the UE, information about the received power levels can be utilized to locate the UE, without the need to process the back-scattered wave [6]. The procedure is divided into two phases that follow a hierarchical and binary tree structure, as depicted in Fig. 2(b).

In phase 1, beam-tracking is performed with RIS-assisted beam-forming, in order to estimate the user's direction with respect to the RIS. In phase 2, ranging is performed with RIS-assisted beam-focusing, in order to estimate the user's distance from the RIS, along the direction identified in phase 1. With information about both the direction and the distance, the location of the UE is fully determined. Essentially, the area in front of the RIS is represented by a polar grid, with the RIS at its origin. The localization resolution is determined by the highest codebook level used in each phase. In phase 1, the angular resolution is determined by the minimum angular beam-width and beam-separation and, in phase 2, the radial resolution is determined by the minimum size of the focal areas formed at each hierarchical level. The performance of the algorithm is demonstrated in Fig. 2(b) for a RIS operating at 150 GHz. The UE is located within a sector of $\pm 25^\circ$ and 10 m extent in front of the RIS, and the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the localization error is presented as a function of the targeted resolution.

2) *Localization with 5GNSS*: Traditionally, location-based services have relied on Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) for positioning. GNSS determines the position of the UE through multilateration, using range measurements from multiple satellites. However, GNSS-based localization is subject to several limitations, including ionospheric and tropospheric disturbances, multipath interference, clock inaccuracies, and satellite visibility loss, typically achieving meter-level accuracy and below. The advent of 5G New Radio (5G-NR) has significantly improved localization precision, offering a promising alternative to overcome the limitations of GNSS. Unlike traditional GNSS, which operates at fixed update rates, 5G-NR enables adaptive, dynamic sensing, allowing real-time position updates at higher temporal resolution.

Fig. 3. Localization with 5GNSS. (a) 3D trajectory comparison of UAV localization methods. (b) 3D positioning errors for tracked UEs over a 5-minute time window. The solid blue line depicts the UAV's distance from the center of the emergency area.

This is particularly beneficial for intelligent transportation systems, Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV)-based monitoring, and industrial automation, where sub-meter precision and low latency are required. The integration of GNSS and 5G-NR within 5GNSS [7] highlights the growing convergence of sensing and communication, demonstrating how ISAC can enable a scalable, network-assisted positioning framework that leverages widely deployed communication infrastructure [8].

In 5GNSS, communication supports sensing by treating 5G-NR not only as a data transmission medium but also as a radio-based localization signal. Unlike standalone GNSS, which struggles in dense urban environments due to signal blockage and multipath effects, 5G-NR provides highly precise Time-of-Flight (ToF) and Direction of Arrival (DoA) measurements, improving accuracy and availability. The fusion of GNSS and 5G-NR ranging information reduces errors from multipath interference and atmospheric delays, making positioning more robust in challenging environments. Fig. 3 demonstrates the performance comparison between a 5GNSS-supported positioning system for UAVs, a GNSS-only-supported positioning system [7] and an oracle system without any positioning errors.

B. Sense-to-communicate

Sensing-aided RIS: As modified RIS hardware now enables dual functionality, i.e. both channel optimizer and passive sensor [9], the RIS transforms into a versatile tool that enhances communication and gathers environmental data, acting as a “sixth sense” for the network. Leveraging sensing information, a self-configuring RIS can autonomously optimize its configuration without relying on a dedicated control channel, instead using local Channel State Information (CSI) obtained via direct sensing.

Such a RIS employs hybrid meta atom hardware with a dual branch architecture that combines reflection and absorption capabilities, as depicted in Fig. 4(a). In the reflection branch, each RIS element reflects a portion (η) of the incoming signal to enhance communication. In the absorption branch, the remaining portion ($1 - \eta$) of the signal is absorbed for sensing and Energy Harvesting (EH). Both branches feature independent, tunable phase shifts, allowing precise control of reflection and absorption. Absorbed signals are directed through an RF circuit for power sensing, enabling accurate

Fig. 4. Sense-to-communicate with RIS. A hybrid RIS with sensing, self-configuration and EH ability for autonomous operation. (a) Architecture and operational modes. (b) Numerical results.

channel estimation. Additionally, an integrated EH module powers the RIS autonomously, eliminating the need for external energy sources.

The hybrid RIS operates in two modes: (a) probing and (b) communication/EH. During probing, the RIS scans the environment by performing directional power measurements to construct a power profile that identifies the Angle of Arrival (AoA) of signals from the Base Station (BS) and UE. This power profile enables local CSI estimation for optimizing both reflected paths (for communication) and absorbed energy (for EH). Specifically, the RIS selects a reflection configuration that maximizes reflected path gains for communication, while aligning absorption configurations to energy rich directions. Harvested power is stored in a rechargeable battery to maintain autonomous operation.

In Fig. 4(b) the average sum rate achieved using the proposed approach is compared with that of a centralized approach that jointly optimizes RIS and BS configurations under perfect CSI. Benchmark tests in multi-user scenarios with varying UE densities and service area sizes show that the proposed approach achieves near optimal communication rates [9]. Furthermore, the EH performance—evaluated under different network traffic conditions (ζ) and various RIS hardware configurations, including phase shift quantization levels (Q) and unit cell power consumption (P_{ON})—demonstrates comparable harvested and consumed, average power. These results highlight the feasibility of the proposed sense-to-communicate approach leveraging local sensing to self optimize communication and EH.

C. Multifunctional ISAC

1) *AI for realistic mobile coverage maps*: The shift towards *beyond communications* requires intelligent systems capable of planning and optimizing the network based on dynamic conditions. Traditional simulation-based methods, though useful, struggle to capture the complexities of the real world, such as building materials, environmental variations, and user

mobility. These models are also computationally intensive and expensive, limiting scalability and agility in future network deployments. As networks advance toward the 6G paradigm, where ultra-dense deployments and precision are key, these limitations become even more pronounced.

AI/ML emerge as transformative enablers, offering the ability to redefine how coverage maps are generated. Leveraging extensive datasets that integrate real-world measurements and parameters of the propagation environment and scatterers (e.g., OpenStreetMap), AI-driven models can increase the situational awareness and capture intricate propagation phenomena, such as signal attenuation, reflections, and diffraction. This enhanced understanding of the environment allows for more efficient and cost-effective network operations, enabling operators to quickly adapt to dynamic conditions and optimize resource management, including RIS deployment optimization in practical environments.

2) *Leveraging self-supervised learning to better exploit long-term sensed information*: Instantaneous sensing data often needs to be interpreted or fused using side information about the large-scale geometric properties of the environment: for instance, a ranging sensor may accurately measure the distance and direction to an obstacle, but a floor map is required to lift the uncertainty about the nature or the size of the sensed object. However, geometric side information such as floor maps or road maps may be costly to gather and maintain, inaccurate, or simply unavailable. Self-supervised ML constitutes a data-driven alternative to interpreting sensed data when little or no geometric side information is available; through organizing and interpreting large amounts of sensing data collected from one or several sensors over the long term, it allows to infer valuable information about the environment without the need for supervision through prior geometric information such as floor maps.

Channel charting is a prime tool to process and interpret large amounts of sensing data, and derive a synthetic view from long-term sensing data [10]. It has been recently proposed to apply dimensionality reduction to the CSI, routinely measured in communication networks. For data associated with a fixed BS, the extracted features are predominantly influenced by the mobile users' large-scale geometric parameters, such as position and orientation. The instantaneous pseudo-position, which can be derived from every CSI measurement through channel charting, is consistent in time and across users, and can be leveraged to enhance positioning applications (through association with a few anchor points, making this a semi-supervised method), or used purely as a self-supervised tool to derive self-consistent contextual information about the relative position of mobile devices connected to the network and/or known obstacles.

3) *Co-design and joint optimization of radar sensing and communications waveforms*: Key components of co-design, optimization, adaptation and learning in ISAC are to build and maintain situational awareness of the dynamic radio environment, create joint objective functions for sensing and communications, define degrees of freedom or operational parameters that can be adapted, as well as specify rewards and regret models for optimization and learning. Sensing

the radio environment, exploiting reciprocity and exchanging information on the state of the spectrum among the cooperative nodes are key capabilities in creating and maintaining situational awareness. Since most of the current and emerging wireless communications systems use multicarrier modulation combined with multiantenna (MIMO) technology, the focus is on designing, optimizing and adapting multicarrier waveforms [11], to achieve the desired performance levels in different sensing and communications tasks, while efficiently using the shared hardware and spectrum resources.

Methods and representations for learning and constructing radio environment awareness facilitate adapting operational parameters and managing resources and interference in ISAC. The adaptation may also consider RIS and wavefront engineering to make the radio environments more favorable. The developed waveform design methods stem from structured and online optimization, model-based and model-free reinforcement learning as well as multicarrier MIMO signal processing. This includes both frequency (subcarrier and resource block) and spatial domain (beamformer, beam, pre-coder and sensor selection) waveform design and resource allocation for ISAC.

The sensing waveforms have task-dependent desirable properties such as a close to ideal ambiguity functions and low peak-to-average-power-ratio. In resource-efficient MIMO systems, launching fewer independent waveforms than transmit (TX) antennas may also be desirable to reduce the number of digital TX channels and thereby costs and power consumption. Operating at this reduced waveform rank without performance loss necessitates carefully designing the waveform and array geometry in a joint manner [12]. There is a variety of sensing tasks with different performance criteria, starting from detecting and resolving targets or objects, estimating target parameters, tracking and recognizing targets and characterizing their micro-Doppler signatures. Hence, different sensing-based services require different waveforms while providing the desired communications performance.

4) *Multi-static sensing in cluttered environments*: To date, a lot of effort has been devoted on mono-static sensing for ISAC, i.e., sensing with the transmitter and receiver being co-located. This leads the transmitted signal to couple directly to the receiver, also known as Self-Interference (SI). If the SI is not efficiently suppressed, it can block the sensing capability completely and, in extreme cases, even damage the receiver. Bi-static sensing, where the transmitter and receiver are in separate locations, can circumvent SI, while allowing for gradual introduction of sensing to cellular networks, in the simplest case requiring only minor changes to the existing cellular network architecture and frame structure or to the hardware of the network nodes.

The bi-static sensing, which can be viewed as a bridge from theoretical ISAC to deployable systems, can be further developed into multi-anchor systems where several nodes perform sensing cooperatively. In rich scattering environments, such as urban areas, the detection of objects with small Radar Cross Section (RCS), such as humans or animals [13], is a challenging task due to strong clutter. To enable sensing under such conditions, techniques such as moving target indication (MTI) can be applied within the co-operative sensing networks

Fig. 5. ISAC evaluation platforms. (a) Hardware evaluation platform in the lab developed at Fraunhofer HHI, for mobile UE and dynamic blockage. Bi-static ISAC measurements are presented using the setup shown in the inset. (b) Hardware-software evaluation platform developed at Barkhausen Institut, for assessing system performance in a mono-static radar and TDD communication operation in the same transceiver system. The radar range measurements are performed with two targets separated by distance of 60 cm, and the communication mode constellation diagram measurements are shown for two selected modulation orders (MO) [14].

to allow the detection, positioning, tracking and identification of the objects in the monitored environment.

V. ISAC EVALUATION PLATFORMS

The merits of ISAC in future generations of wireless connectivity will have to be validated by means of experimental platforms and testbeds that cover the breadth of envisioned application scenarios. The use cases are comprised of both indoor and outdoor applications in more or less controlled environments. Modeling this catalogue accurately is a challenge, which can be addressed by miniaturizing the setup in scale while retaining the possibility to introduce characteristic elements of the driving use cases such as blockages, movement, or multi-path components into the ISAC testbed.

Fig. 5(a) depicts a small-scale ISAC evaluation platform, for experimentally exploring the possibilities and challenges of wideband ISAC systems with transceivers from 28 GHz up to 300 GHz. A fixed ISAC node at the top of the cell represents a BS, with ample space reserved for bulkier and more capable signal generation and processing equipment. Dynamic elements are introduced by affixing the UE node, a RIS unit, or reflective surfaces for generating NLoS components to the sides or struts of the cage, enabling the exploration of varying usage scenarios and the investigation of impairments, such as increased frequency selectivity of the deployed hardware. A robotic arm is mounted to the base of the cell, offering highly precise positioning and maneuvering of antenna frontends or other objects. Lastly, state-of-the-art test and measurement equipment such as a 100 GSa/s DAC and 20 GHz BW ADC

support wideband signal generation and reception and reduce the reliance on hardware via digital modulation and demodulation capabilities. In the ISAC measurements presented in Fig. 5(a), a TX antenna array at a fixed position illuminates a brushed copper plate with a communication waveform, organized into frames with a header and payload section each. A Receiver (RX) antenna array mounted to a robotic arm moves on a circular trajectory around the center point of the plate. At each waypoint, the header is evaluated to obtain an estimate of the path length relative to a reference signal sent directly from DAC to ADC. A coarse delay estimate is given by the time difference of the estimated frame start positions (measured in integer samples) and subsequently refined by analyzing the sub-sample delay (measured as slope of the estimated channel phase responses). This two-stage approach offers a stable and accurate estimate of the constant path length (including cable assemblies), even if the received power at the ADC is low due to the receiver gradually moving away from the maximum of the specular reflection.

Fig. 5(b) illustrates a hardware-software evaluation platform designed to assess system performance in a mono-static radar and Time-Division-Duplex (TDD) communication operation in the same transceiver system [14]. The custom RX front-end features high-isolation antennas and is reconfigurable, allowing it to switch between high-linearity and high-gain modes. The high-linearity mode enhances the detection of nearby targets, while the high-gain mode compensates for path loss when detecting distant objects or transmitters. The communication RX can be either the same reconfigurable RX or a different RX. Fig. 5(b) shows one such example, where the RX front-end consists of a Low-Noise Amplifier (LNA) and a down-conversion mixer. The RX operates at the 5G-NR n258 band and supports a 2.5 GHz bandwidth to meet radar operation requirements. The RX chip is fabricated with 22 nm Fully Depleted Silicon-On-Insulator (FDSOI) technology and is integrated onto a PCB along with a dedicated DC supply board. The antennas demonstrate 40 dB isolation across the band. Antenna isolation prevents receiver saturation, enabling mono-static radar operation and, if needed, in-band full-duplex communication. A digital Self-Interference Cancellation (SIC) scheme is also embedded within the link-level evaluator [15]. The TX is built using off-the-shelf components, although custom TX can be used as well. The Universal Software Defined Radio Peripheral (USRP) handles both transmission and reception of waveforms, which are generated and processed by the Heterogeneous Mobile Radio Simulator Python (HermesPy) [15]. HermesPy evaluates receiver performance across various signal processing algorithms. The USRP enables high-performance, multi-channel, wide-band signal generation and analysis. The platform offers a versatile testbed for various waveforms and operation characteristics. The radar measurements are performed using co-located antennas and a corner reflector as the target; the communication measurements are performed in a line-of-sight scenario with the same RX hardware. To estimate the range-power profile, HermesPy correlates transmitted frames with their corresponding digital counterparts sampled at the RX. Radar capabilities are assessed using range-power profiles, while communication performance

is evaluated through eye and constellation diagrams at different modulation orders [14], as demonstrated in the multi-target scenario presented in Fig. 5(b).

The two platforms empower the design, testing and development of multifunctional ISAC techniques, in a synergetic and complementary way; the hardware platform equipped with the robotic arm offers a controlled environment for mono-static sensing with wideband signal operation, while the hardware-software platform equipped with HermesPy on USRP performs mono-static sensing with full-duplex communication. Hence, the combination of the two platforms can be key to achieving unprecedented data throughput and sensing resolution for multiple use cases, and to showcasing the potential custom hardware solutions in making ISAC a reality.

VI. CONCLUSION

Until recently, most emphasis has been placed on designing communication networks for reliable transmission of large volumes of data. As 6G networks go beyond broadband data transmission, integrating sensing and communication becomes essential for providing multi-functional connectivity, taking into account environmental parameters and usage scenario characteristics. In this article, the roadmap for ISAC was analyzed for future interactive, immersive, and intelligent connectivity beyond just communications. Three visionary pillars were presented, namely sense-to-communicate, communicate-to-sense, and multifunctional ISAC connectivity, from the synthesis of which ISAC is envisioned to emerge. The multifunctional capabilities (e.g. situational awareness, environmental mapping) of ISAC were discussed and innovative technologies that are expected to play a crucial role in future wireless connectivity were presented. Two hardware/software testbeds were also presented for experimentally exploring the possibilities and challenges of ISAC systems.

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